

PATHOLOGICAL ANATOMY AND PROBLEMS OF MODERN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Modern education at a medical university has its own characteristics and is becoming one of the most pressing problems of our time. The issue of teaching the discipline "Pathological Anatomy" is limited not only by the ability of students to study the subject, the material base of the department. The most pressing problems of the educational process at a university seem to be not the introduction of increasingly complex and expensive visual aids, not computerization or overloading students with increasingly numerous and colorful atlases, but the structural restructuring of the process and its proper financing.

The state of the educational system in the modern world is extremely contradictory. On the one hand, education in the twentieth century has become one of the most important areas of human activity, and in the second half of the last century, more people were trained in the education system in the world than in the entire previous history of mankind.

Enormous achievements in the field of education formed the basis for grandiose social transformations and scientific and technological progress. On the other hand, the rapid expansion of the sphere of education and changes in its status are accompanied by a sharp aggravation of problems in this area in the 21st century.

What makes our education system advanced is not computers and interactive whiteboards, but real people with up-to-date knowledge and skills.

Modern education at a medical university has its own characteristics and is currently turning into one of the most pressing problems of our time.

The conflict between society's need for increasingly massive training of specialists, in particular doctors, on the one hand, and the practical impossibility of realizing this need, on the other.

The society is replenished with young doctors every year, and yet there is a shortage of specialists not only in highly qualified, but also in the most common specialties. At the moment, there are approximately 20–25 percent of students who are able to master the discipline we teach, and, according to official statistics, about 80 percent graduate from the university. Along with this, the number of medical universities has increased, which has made it more accessible to enter a university,

but not the level, and, consequently, the quality of higher education, because the availability of the latter is determined by the mental and physical capabilities of the student.

A decrease in the level of preparedness of applicants entails a simplification of the presentation of educational material, the investment of effort and money in the production of new and rather expensive macro- and microscopic preparations and other items designed to facilitate the assimilation of a very complex science that studies various aspects of the disease. For the same purpose, various tables and diagrams are introduced into textbooks, but ultimately all this leads to the denial of the main postulate on which higher education is based: the main type of educational activity of a student is independent work.

Practical classes are necessary to test the level of students' mastery of the material, while lectures are provided to explain the theoretical foundations. Therefore, the more the teacher himself covers the topic, the less students work independently, which results in a decrease in the requirements for the level of knowledge.

Pathomorphology studies the structural (material) basis of the disease, therefore pathological anatomy is both a fundamental and applied discipline. The theoretical significance is revealed when studying the general patterns of pathology development, while the clinical component is revealed when creating a model of a sick person. Students need to have in-depth knowledge of the structure of the body, tissues at the macro- and microscopic levels. When studying pathological processes and diseases, it is necessary to have information about the causes of occurrence, development mechanisms, the morphological basis of these mechanisms, disease outcomes, complications, death, thanatogenesis. Students need to acquire a certain amount of knowledge before starting to study pathological anatomy.

In relation to the Department of Human Pathological Anatomy, the problem under discussion has another aspect. The vast majority of students cannot cope with the given pace, and there is a need to prolong the time allocated for studying pathological anatomy, especially when studying a private course, and the expected change in the curriculum will have the opposite effect.

There is no doubt about the need for scientific research by university teachers. Scientific work is carried out within the framework of educational and methodological work, research activities attract students to work in a scientific circle, and prepare future young scientists. In addition, scientific work contributes to the training of a new generation of teachers who are not trained anywhere except in departments. Currently, this topic is complicated by the low salary of teachers in the Department of Pathological Anatomy and, therefore, the need to combine teaching not with scientific work, but with any other work, including part-time work. Meanwhile, scientific work in the field of human pathological anatomy is associated with a large investment of time already at the stage of obtaining the material to be studied: studying case histories, selecting blocks, making histological preparations, their staining, microscopy, application of morphological programs, statistical processing, publication of the obtained data.

Thus, the issue of teaching the discipline "Pathological Anatomy" is limited not only by the ability of students to study the subject, the material base of the department, but also by insufficient personnel potential, the low level of graduation of teachers, the reluctance of young specialists to work in state universities and engage in research work with subsequent defense.

Consequently, the most pressing problems of the educational process at a university seem to be not the introduction of increasingly complex and expensive visual aids, not computerization or overloading students with increasingly numerous and colorful atlases, but the structural restructuring of the process and its proper financing.

References:

1. Gessen S.I. Fundamentals of pedagogy. Introduction to Applied Philosophy. M.: Shkola-Press, 1995. 448 p.
2. Zagvyazinsky V.I. Learning theory: A modern interpretation. M.: Publishing center "Academy", 2001. 192 p.
3. Baglaev G.P. Methods of vocational training. Educational and methodological manual. Ulan-Ude: Buryat State University Publishing House, 2009. 106 p.
4. Baglaev G.P., Darkhanov V.I. Some problems of vocational pedagogical education in the Republic of Belarus // Education and globalization. Proceedings of the 2nd international conference dedicated to the 85th anniversary of the birth of academician P.R. Atutova. Ulan-Ude, 2006. pp. 103–105.
5. Baglaev G.P. General and professional pedagogy. Educational and methodological manual. Ulan-Ude: Buryat State University Publishing House, 2009. 55 p.

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